

Next-Generation Tuberculosis Diagnostics: A Detailed Review of Emerging Tools and Global Trends

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ABSTRACT:

Tuberculosis (TB), caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, continues to be one of the world's most serious infectious diseases, with millions of new cases and deaths annually. Timely and accurate diagnosis remains a cornerstone for effective management and control. Conventional approaches such as sputum smear microscopy, chest radiography, and culture media still play an important role, particularly in resource-limited settings, but are limited by sensitivity, specificity, and turnaround time. Immunological tests, including the tuberculin skin test and interferon-gamma release assays, have been widely used but struggle to differentiate between latent and active infection. Recent advances in molecular and innovative diagnostic technologies—such as nucleic acid amplification tests (GeneXpert, TrueNAT), line probe assays, and polymerase chain reaction techniques—have greatly improved detection accuracy and drug resistance profiling. Emerging approaches, including next-generation sequencing, nanotechnology, biosensors, and artificial intelligence-based diagnostic tools, offer promising solutions for rapid, affordable, and decentralized testing. Despite significant progress, challenges remain regarding accessibility, affordability, and integration into healthcare systems. Strengthening diagnostic capacity through combined conventional and novel methods is essential to achieve effective TB control and move closer to global eradication goals.

KEYWORDS:

Tuberculosis, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, diagnosis, smear microscopy, GeneXpert, NAAT.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) is the causative agent of tuberculosis (TB), an airborne illness that typically affects the lungs and causes intense coughing, fever, and chest pains (1). Early pulmonary TB detection remains a challenge for clinicians, and quick TB diagnosis can be tough in clinical practice. For TB control, early detection of active pulmonary TB is crucial for both individual treatment and public health initiatives to stop the disease's spread across the community. Although it has a low and variable sensitivity, sputum smear microscopy is a quick, easy, and affordable method of diagnosing pulmonary tuberculosis. Both molecular and non-molecular assays have recently been created for the early identification of active tuberculosis, either with or without the discovery of treatment resistance (2). The interferon γ release (IGRA) test and the tuberculin skin test are used to identify latent infection. Smear microscopy is frequently used to diagnose active tuberculosis (3). New detection techniques, including RNA sequencing and proteomics, which have greater sensitivity and specificity, speed, simplicity, and ease of use, have been progressively used to diagnose latent infections in recent years due to the quick growth of molecular biology technology (4).

2. CONVENTIONAL DIAGNOSTIC METHODS:

Effective treatment and prompt diagnosis are critical to TB control. Because of its low sensitivity, conventional smear microscopy cannot detect this bacterium's drug resistance. Since the results are often available after three to four weeks, the standard culture-based diagnosis takes a lot of time. Diagnostic immunology techniques are unable to distinguish between latent and active TB, while molecular biology techniques are unable to distinguish between live and dead *M. tuberculosis*. The need for straightforward, quick, precise, and cost-effective point-of-care methods has grown in recent years due to the shortcomings of the current detection methods as well as the ongoing growth of multidrug-resistant and extensively drug-resistant TB.(5).

2.1. SPUTUM SMEAR MICROSCOPY:

In the most common locations, sputum microscopy is quick, cheap, and remarkably specific. It has been the worldwide approach to tuberculosis control. Sputum smear microscopy is probably going to be the only sustainable technology in environments with low resources. The only economical method for identifying patients with infectious TB and tracking their treatment outcomes is sputum smear microscopy. The ability of smear microscopy to identify species is limited by its ability to detect the presence or absence of acid-fast bacteria. (6).

UPDATE:

Along with increasing smear microscopy's sensitivity, fluorescence microscopy can reduce labour costs and boost productivity. While fluorescence microscopy requires a powerful light source, such as a halogen or high-pressure mercury vapour lamp, which is both costly and susceptible, ordinary microscopy employs conventional artificial light (7).

2.2 CHEST X-RAY:

Since both forms of TB have different radiological patterns, chest X-rays (CXR) are a crucial tool for TB screening. One of the most accurate methods for identifying active tuberculosis is chest radiography. 5. Digital radiography technology has advanced, but there are still drawbacks, such as limited access in low-resource settings, variability between and within readers, and low specificity, particularly in endemic areas with high HIV prevalence

and a history of prior tuberculosis. 6. However, the emergence of computer-aided detection (CAD) based on artificial intelligence has presented a possible chance to expedite screening methods by identifying radiological anomalies linked to tuberculosis early.(8)

UPDATE:

According to studies, CAD is a sensitive instrument that can interpret chest x-rays as accurately as or more accurately than skilled human readers (8).

2.3. CULTURE MEDIUM:

Both liquid (like Middlebrook 7H9) and solid (like Lowenstein–Jensen) media can be used for traditional Mtb culture. Notably, liquid culture is quicker, more sensitive, and more convenient (growth is recognised automatically). Still, solid culture is less costly and less likely to be contaminated by other bacteria or fungi. Sample decontamination is a technical detail that needs to be disclosed. Before being cultured, samples (like sputum) contaminated with regular flora must be decontaminated. Regular decontamination reagents like NaOH and N-acetyl-L-cysteine (NALC) can be used in the lab; they destroy fast-growing bacteria and fungi but have little effect on Mtb growth. To prevent over-decontamination, which lowers the yield of Mtb, and under-decontamination, which results in failed cultures due to excessive rates of bacterial or fungal growth, the laboratory should ascertain the ideal concentration of the decontamination reagent. (9).

3. IMMUNOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS:

The most popular commercially available TB immunodiagnostic techniques are still the tuberculin skin test and interferon gamma (IFN- γ) release assays (IGRAs). However, because IGRAs do not help diagnose active TB disease—a significant issue in regions with high latent infection prevalence—their use is restricted in high TB endemic areas. As instruments for tracking the response to TB treatment, IGRAs have also produced erratic results. There has been promise in the detection of host indicators other than IFN- γ following overnight stimulation with the antigens used in IGRAs (ESAT-6/CFP-10/TB7.7) and in the production of markers following stimulation with novel M.tb infection phase-dependent antigens. Assays based on overnight cultures, however, cannot be used as quick, point-of-care testing. Serum, plasma, saliva, and other ex vivo samples contain host biomarkers that have demonstrated promise in the detection of tuberculosis (10).

3.1. TUBERCULIN SKIN TEST:

Based on the idea of a type IV allergic reaction, the TST is a conventional diagnostic technique. Pure tuberculin protein derivatives are used in this in vivo skin test to cause a hypersensitive reaction. Bacillus Calmette-Guerin Pure Protein Derivative (BCG-PPD) and tuberculin Pure Protein Derivative (TB-PPD) are the two main skin tests used in China. An accelerated stability test has shown that BCG-PPD, a protein isolated from the human-type pathogen MTB, has satisfactory long-term stability. The BCG-PPD preparation is made from the culture filtrate of BCG. There has been a movement to create alternative tests because of the TST's low specificity. As a result, novel skin tests have been developed, such as the recombinant Mycobacterium tuberculosis fusion protein (EC) created in China, the Diaskintest reagent created in Russia, and the C-TB reagent created in Denmark. 26 The basic idea behind how these reagents work is the same (4).

UPDATE:

To get over TST's drawbacks, the Interferon Gamma Release Test (IGRT) was created more recently. In nations where the BCG vaccine is widely used and the

corresponding false-positive rate of TST is high, IGRT might be more accurate than TST (9). Although IGRT offers the advantages of not cross-reacting with BCG, having no reinforcing effect, not requiring re-evaluation, and producing findings in 24 to 48 hours (10), it requires a laboratory setting, is expensive, and is unable to detect latent infection (11).

3.2 INTERFERON-GAMMA RELEASE ASSAY (IGRA):

The IGRA is an in vitro test that uses the host immune system's reaction to particular MTB antigens to identify the existence of a bacterial infection. The amount of gamma-interferon (IFN- γ) emitted by activated T cells is measured to accomplish this. The two main tests that make up IGRA are the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and the enzyme-linked immunospot assay (ELISPOT). Both assays use culture filtrate protein 10 (CFP-10) and early secretory antigen target 6 (ESAT-6) as specific antigens (4).

When two commercial IGRA tests were compared head-to-head, it was shown that QuantiFERON-TB Gold In-Tube was slightly less sensitive than T-SPOT but more specific. TB However, among discordant instances, QuantiFERON Gold was noticeably more accurate than T-SPOT TB in identifying true-positive cases of tuberculous uveitis. IGRA's drawbacks include its high cost and inability to distinguish between latent and active infections. Because anti-IFN- γ autoantibodies may affect the test's positivity, a negative IGRA cannot rule out tuberculosis. As a result, IGRA alone is insufficient to diagnose OTB, particularly in areas where TB endemicity is high (12). Because IGRAs are more costly and call for specific lab equipment, low- and middle-income nations might not have easy access to it. Additionally, about 1 in 26 IGRA tests have indeterminate findings, especially for immunocompromised people and young children (13).

UPDATE:

Three new IGRAs— (1) Advansure TB IGRA (LG Chem, Seoul, Republic of Korea), (2) Lioferon TB/LTBI (LIONEX Diagnostics & Therapeutics GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany), and (3) Quantiferon-Diasorin (Stillwater, MN, USA)—are under review for potential WHO policy recommendations (13).

4. MOLECULAR DIAGNOSIS:

4.1. LIPOARABINOMANNAN ASSAY:

A commercial point-of-care test called LF-LAM can identify lipoarabinomannan (LAM), a part of bacterial cell walls that some individuals with active tuberculosis have. The exam is easy to complete and yields results in twenty-five minutes. Culture or molecular testing (benchmark) was used to compare LF-LAM results. Over time, there has been a lot of interest in the detection of mycobacterial antigen in urine. A non-site-specific diagnosis of tuberculosis would be possible with urine-based antigen testing. Urine also doesn't carry the same infection control problems as sputum and is simple to collect and store. Initially, lipoarabinomannan (LAM), a component of mycobacterial cell walls, was detected using a variety of platforms, including enzyme-linked immunosorbent (ELISA) tests that were assessed in a number of clinical contexts (14).

4.2. LINE PROBE ASSAY:

To detect resistance-associated mutations in Mtb against rifampin (RIF), isoniazid (INH), fluoroquinolones (FQ), second-line injectable (SLI) drugs (such as amikacin [AM], capreomycin [CM], streptomycin [STR], and kanamycin [KM]), and ethambutol (EMB), sputum- based assays (LPA) are used in conjunction with rapid molecular TB drug-resistance testing(14).

Similar to other probe-based assays, line probe tests have the drawback of only being able to detect the most common mutations; in other cases, they depend on the negative hybridisation result with the WT-specific probe as a marker for other mutations. It might be challenging to determine the importance of a found mutation because no sequence data are given and not all mutations result in treatment resistance (15). The manufacturer's protocol was followed when performing the LPA. The three components of the test—DNA extraction, multiplex PCR amplification, and reverse hybridization—are based on DNA strip technology (16).

4.3. POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTIONS:

For the reactions of DNA denaturation and enzymatic DNA replication, the PCR assay technique relies on "thermal cycling," which consists of cycles with repeated heating and cooling. DNA polymerase and short DNA fragments known as "primers" that contain sequences complementary to the target area are essential for enabling sequence-specific DNA amplification. Both the primer sequence setting that closely resembles the template sequence and the annealing temperature setting that varies according to primer length are the primary causes of PCR's specificity. After attaching itself to the primer-template combination, the DNA polymerase starts the synthesis of new DNA. The produced DNA fragment is employed as a replication template while the heat cycling process goes on, starting a "chain reaction" that amplifies the DNA template exponentially. When EtBr is intercalated into the main groove of DNA, it fluoresces under UV light. After EtBr treatment, the amplified target DNA fragment may be seen and identified as a characteristic band (17). By employing the reverse-transcription technique, RT-PCR can be utilized to quantify the pathogen burden in the sample and to amplify both DNA and RNA. There are numerous PCR kits that are sold commercially.

UPDATE:

The cartridge-based nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT), also known as GeneXpert, is a new technique that was discovered by the laboratories of Professor Alland at New Jersey (USA), Cepheid Inc. (USA), and FIND, with funding from the National Institutes of Health, USA. (18).

5. NEW TECHNIQUES:

5.1 GENE XPRT ASSAY:

By identifying MTB DNA and rifampicin resistance in a matter of hours, "The GeneXpert- MTB/RIF assay," a quick molecular test frequently used for TB, has proven effective in diagnosing ETB (19). Following the manufacturer's instructions, Xpert was applied to the respiratory specimens. In a nutshell, 2 mL of Xpert sample reagent (a combination of NaOH and isopropanol) was combined with 1 mL of each respiratory specimen in the Falcon tube. Following a 15-minute incubation period at room temperature, 2 mL of the digested sample was moved to the designated cartridge and put into the Xpert machine. The Xpert system indicated semi-quantified bacillary load as high, medium, low, or extremely low, along with the presence or absence of tubercle bacilli. (20).

UPDATE:

The most utilized for TB diagnosis and detecting rifampicin resistance is GeneXpert MTB/RIF, with its upgraded version being GeneXpert Ultra (21).

5.2 NUCLEIC ACID AMPLIFICATION TEST (NAAT):

With certain tests (such as Cepheid Xpert MTB/RIF, henceforth referred to as “Xpert MTB/RIF”), nucleic acid amplification (NAA) testing can concurrently detect medication resistance and quickly identify MTBC straight from clinical specimens (22). Only rudimentary laboratory knowledge and little infrastructure are needed for these low-complexity automated nucleic acid amplification tests (LC-aNAATs). Evaluation of sputum and LC-a NAATs on respiratory samples is crucial for the diagnosis of tuberculosis (23).

TrueNAT and CBNAAT/Gene Xpert are the two NAAT varieties that are now on the market. There is little to no fluctuation in the results of any test, which is objective. Within two hours, CBNAAT/Gene Xpert may identify *M. tuberculosis* bacteria and concurrently identify rifampicin resistance in biological samples; nevertheless, it needs constant electricity and sophisticated lab equipment. On the other hand, TrueNAT doesn't need a sophisticated lab setup and can function without electricity (24).

5.3. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNIQUE:

Researchers have the opportunity and technical foundation to create innovative, accurate, quick, and automated tools for pulmonary tuberculosis care, including but not limited to tuberculosis detection, thanks to artificial intelligence (AI), which is not new but has recently gained popularity (25). Deep learning-based computer-aided detection (CAD) systems that are based on artificial intelligence (AI) present a viable way to identify PTB automatically. In order to further AI applications in TB screening and diagnosis, we conducted a meta-analysis to assess the diagnostic accuracy of five AI-based PTB detection products (26) Overcome in order to develop and deploy AI-assisted diagnosis tools for PTB. These include limited data quality and availability, a lack of standardisation, bias and ethical considerations, interpretability and explainability, and integration into clinical workflow (27).

5.4. NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING:

Despite its high cost, NGS has become a potent method for identifying drug resistance in *Mtb* isolates. Compared to conventional phenotypic DST, NGS-based techniques for DST have a number of benefits, such as increased sensitivity and the capacity to identify many resistance variants at once (28). Targeted NGS can fulfill the demand for swift resistance forecasting for both first-line and second-line anti-tuberculosis medications. Acknowledging its potential, the WHO endorsed targeted NGS for genotypic drug susceptibility testing of drug-resistant tuberculosis in March 2024 and labeled it as one of its research and development priorities for tuberculosis diagnostic tools. (29).

5.5. NANOTECHNOLOGY:

In recent years, TB tests have improved thanks to nanomaterials. More response sites are made possible by their high surface area-to-volume ratio, which significantly improves detection sensitivity and permits precise TB detection even at low bacterial loads. Detection systems based on nanomaterials often produce quick results. For instance, numerous TB indicators can be detected simultaneously thanks to the nanomaterials' ability to attach to numerous molecules.

Metal nanoparticles enhance tuberculosis diagnostics by mitigating some conventional limitations. Thanks to their optical, electronic, and magnetic properties, they can be modified with various ligands to detect tuberculosis biomarkers at low concentrations. Additionally, they can be engineered to be portable and user-friendly, facilitating convenient use at medical treatment locations. This enables the implementation of decentralized testing in resource-limited settings, making diagnostic tests potentially more cost-effective. (30).

5.6. BIOSENSORS:

Generally speaking, a biosensor for *M. tuberculosis* detection is a small analytical instrument that combines a physicochemical transducer and a biological sensing element. Biosensors based on antibodies and nucleic acids have been developed, depending on the biological element used. Piezoelectric, electrochemical, and optical biosensors for *M. tuberculosis* detection can be separated based on signal transduction techniques (31).

One of the most important uses of nanotechnology in recent decades has been the widespread use of nanobiosensors, or biosensors based on nanomaterials, in the diagnosis of tuberculosis. Typically, a biosensor is composed of two components: the signal transduction component, which transforms biological signals into other signal types like optical or electrical signals, and the biorecognition component, which binds and enriches target chemicals to produce biological signals. Because of their remarkable optical, electrical, and mechanical characteristics, nanomaterials are very useful in biosensors for amplifying and converting biomolecular signals (32).

6. CONCLUSION:

Therefore, it is essential to diagnose and detect this disease as soon as possible. Numerous techniques, like the PCR-based GeneXpert approach and the Mantoux tuberculin skin test, have been employed over the years to identify tuberculosis (33). Despite their great sensitivity and specificity, molecular-based diagnostic techniques necessitate expensive laboratory infrastructures and highly qualified individuals to conduct tests. However, because they are practical, reliable, and affordable, traditional laboratory methods for diagnosing tuberculosis are still frequently used despite their numerous shortcomings. Furthermore, to ascertain its medication susceptibility, phenotypic susceptibility testing is still necessary. Thus, for the conclusive laboratory diagnosis of tuberculosis, acid-fast smear microscopy, culture-based methods, and nucleic acid amplification tests (NAATs) are presently used (34).

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